

CAREER GUIDANCE FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH TECHNOLOGY LESSONS

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Abstract

Among the ways to introduce students to the world of labor and professions, the subject of "Technology" plays an important role. This article discusses improving the methodology of technology education to strengthen the material base of the subject, enhance the connection between the school and the surrounding industries and agriculture, organize socially useful and productive labor, increase its educational and economic effectiveness, and integrate it with teaching in order to improve the preparation of students for work.

Keywords: professional competence, production, career guidance, primary education.

The changes occurring in the education sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan are being recognized globally as one of the key factors ensuring the country's future. In the current stage of educational reforms, the issue of nurturing a free-thinking individual has gained particular importance. In our country, the role of the technology education teacher is indispensable in fulfilling the social mandate of preparing students to work effectively in various sectors of the national economy, to consciously choose their professions, and to acquire professional skills.

To accomplish this state task, the technology education teacher must continuously improve their knowledge, skills, and competencies in general labor, as well as stay in line with the dynamic demands of the evolving pedagogical process. This requires mastery of the achievements in pedagogy, psychology, methodology, modern technology, advanced manufacturing technologies, and market economy relations. Moreover, they must acquire in-depth knowledge, skills, and competencies in these areas.

In this context, it is essential to enhance the scope and quality of the technology teacher's knowledge, skills, and competencies, to ensure the successful organization and implementation of the educational process based on the National Curriculum requirements, and to address any shortcomings in their professional practice. Furthermore, improving the teacher's professional skills

and their complex and multifaceted activities in labor-related fields is of paramount importance.

The technology lesson has its own distinctive features when applying general didactic principles to other subjects in school. Students are engaged not only in cognitive activities but also in creative activities. The subject, tools, and processes of technology should not just be studied as simple objects of learning; instead, they should serve as tools that activate students' practical work, didactic materials, and technical means of education.

The goal of teaching technology is to educate students who are well-rounded and developed, trained in the spirit of modern times, and capable of solving current problems related to organizing and implementing education and upbringing in the era of market economy. These students should be able to deeply feel and incorporate the national independence idea, our national and universal human values into the content of education and upbringing.

In order for students to master the subject of technology, it is important to use advanced and modern teaching methods, and to implement new information-pedagogical technologies. Using textbooks, handouts, electronic materials, production samples, and models in the learning process helps students gain a broader understanding of professions. Choosing a profession is a very important issue, and often students are unable to make this decision independently. In this matter, the school should assist them. In technology lessons, the teacher should provide each student with a card and conduct a "Survey" about the student's attitude toward different subjects, their interest in professions, academic achievements, and personal qualities. This helps to determine the student's areas of interest. If the student's interests are stable, the teacher will start assessing whether the student possesses the necessary traits for the profession they wish to choose. In some cases, a student's health may not meet the requirements of the profession they are considering. This issue is determined based on a doctor's recommendation. When students are choosing a profession, teachers should not overly insist on influencing their decisions. In this case, it is very important to be cautious and to determine whether the student's interest in the profession is genuine or just a temporary curiosity. The process of guiding students in choosing a profession should take into account the actual working conditions of the school. The guidance on choosing a profession has a special place in the lower grades. On the one hand, the profession guidance continues directly in the labor lessons, where students learn about the professions related to the field they have chosen for vocational training. In this way, the students'

interest in a profession gradually "narrows down." On the other hand, the process of guiding students starts with the topics in the Technology textbooks, which introduce students to the main professions and specializations in the national economy. A student who undergoes an extended vocational training process will master various elements of related professions. As a result, they will gain initial vocational skills. The freedom to choose a profession manifests itself in this contradiction. The entire content, forms, and methods of career guidance are aimed at achieving this goal. From the above, it can be concluded that the process of guiding students in choosing a profession involves several stages, and at each stage, specific tasks are addressed. In this regard, the guidance on choosing a profession, like any other educational and developmental process, consists of a two-way process, where equal importance is given to both the teacher and the student. Therefore, the most important requirement for the profession guidance process is that the students must be highly active, and this activity is ensured through vocational education and the development of the foundational principles of career choice. If labor education teachers are well-prepared for professional diagnosis and career counseling, and if these tasks are carried out on time, students' activity levels will increase.

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